

BROKEN BONDS AS SEATS OF ION EXCHANGE IN CRYSTALLINE SILICATES

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Many crystalline silicates take up cations from solutions in contact with the solid phase in exchange for cations already present in the solid. These exchangeable cations are essential constituents of the silicate lattice being held opposite potentially negative positions of the lattice and still accessible to the cations of the 'contact solution.' The cation exchange capacity of a given weight of the mineral often markedly increases on grinding it to extreme fineness, as by this process a large number of cations, originally located in the interior of the lattice, is exposed and made accessible to the cations of the contact solution. Of particular interest is the cation binding capacity of silicates having sheetlike structures, *e.g.*, kaolinite, in which the sheets themselves are neutral being made up of Si-O tetrahedra and Al-O (or, OH) octahedra. There are no metal cations in the lattice (required for balancing negative charges arising from isomorphous replacements) which can be exchanged for those of an added electrolyte and yet finely ground kaolinite has been found to take up cations from solutions to the extent of 100.5 milliequivalents per 100 g. of the solid (Kelley and Jenny, *Soil Sci.*, 1936, 41, 367). To what is this cation binding power due? One answer to this question which has been frequently given will be examined here. It has been suggested that the cations are held on the lateral surfaces of the sheets where unsatisfied valencies are developed as a result of lattice termination (Hendricks, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, 37, 625). The lateral surface increases on grinding which produces fracture parallel to the c-axis by breaking valence bonds between Si and O, and between Al and O (or, OH). The fact that the cation binding capacity of kaolinite increases on grinding (Kelley *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) is, on this theory, to be attributed to an increase in the number of the broken bonds.

An important aspect of these broken bonds appears to have been either overlooked, or, misunderstood. To appreciate this we shall first consider what happens when the bond between two linked tetrahedra or octahedra breaks, *i.e.*, when an Si-O-Si bond, or, an Al-O (or, OH)-Al bond is ruptured. Evidently, the oxygen ion can go with only one of the silicons (or aluminiums) linked by it, and the OH ion, with only one of the aluminiums. The Si or Al, which takes the O or OH, becomes negatively charged and a positive charge is left with the other Si or Al. Taking next the case of a linear silicate polymer, *i.e.*, a pyroxene, the "principle of microscopic neutrality" requires that potentially positive and negative ends or poles be produced simultaneously and in equal numbers by the rupture of the Si-O-Si bonds. Comminution of any ionic crystal would proceed on the same principle and fractures of kaolinite crystals parallel to the c-axis would be no exception. The finely ground solid would therefore *tend* to take up equal number of cations and anions from a contact solution and not merely cations as Kelley and Jenny (*loc. cit.*) argue in criticising Hofmann's suggestion (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1934, 47, 539) that the exchangeable cations in layer-lattice silicates are held by broken bonds on the edges of the Si-O planes. Their criticism would be certainly valid if only a cation binding power were attributed to the broken bonds. Actually, however, the bonds would tend to bind

both cations and anions. In other words, *the bonds, as they break, give a potentially amphoteric character to the comminuted solid.*

Whether the broken bonds in a given ionic crystal will at all remove cations and anions from a contact solution to the solid phase is a question is left open for the present. In a search for the relevant factors one would perhaps have to bring in considerations of the actual strengths and separations of the positive and negative poles, the extent to which the bonds are ionic, the structural peculiarities of the surface and specific properties, e.g., valency, polarisability, size and state of hydration of the cations and anions of the contact solution. The broken bonds may even be satisfied by adsorbing oriented water dipoles. Fuller discussion of these aspects is deferred pending completion of investigations on them, now in progress. What is intended to be emphasised here is that if a cation binding power is at all attributed to the broken bonds, as has been done by Hendricks (*loc. cit.*), Hofmann *et al* (*loc. cit.*), Grim (*J. Geol.*, 1942, 51, 225) and others in the case of certain layer-lattice aluminosilicates, an anion binding capacity of these minerals due to the same cause has also to be recognised, i.e., the minerals must be considered amphoteric and not merely acidic. This aspect of broken Si-O-Si and Al-O (or, OH)-Al bonds deserves careful consideration in view of Mattson's experiments (*Soil Sci.*, 1931, 32, 143) which show that soil colloids now known to consist principally of certain well known aluminosilicates of the layer-lattice type do possess an amphoteric character. Hydrargillite containing Al-OH-Al bonds is definitely amphoteric. The available evidence is unfortunately inconclusive on the question of broken Si-O-Si bonds of quartz as sites for ionic exchange. Kelley and Jenny failed to detect any appreciable cation binding power of the ground mineral. Jackson and Truog (*Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1939, 4, 136), on the other hand, report a cation binding capacity to the extent of 60.0 m.e. per 100 g. No data on the anion binding power of ground quartz are available. Apparently, further work on pure specimens of this and other minerals is necessary.